

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Paper

Metabolites Profiling of An Anti-Urease and Free Radical Scavenging Fraction from the Acetone Leaves Extract of *Microsorium Pustulatum* (G. Frost) Copel (Polypodiaceae)

Olebunne B. O.¹, Afierohe O. E.^{1,2}, Suleiman M.*¹, Abo K. A.¹

¹Department of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

²Nuclei for Phytomedicines and Chemical Ecology (NuPaCE), Central Research Laboratory for Phytomedicine, Department of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 02 May 2025

Keywords:

Microsorium pustulatum,
Polypodiaceae, Adamantane,
oxime, polyacetylenic
alcohol Urease inhibitor

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14927280

ABSTRACT

Background: As a follow-up to an earlier report on the anti-urease and free radical scavenging potentials of the extracts and partitioned solvent fractions from the leaves of the epiphytic fern *Microsorium pustulatum*, this study is reporting the metabolites' profile of an active chromatography fraction using Gas Chromatography- Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). **Method:** The bioactive acetone extract obtained after prior defatting with n-hexane was further partitioned between chloroform and water to obtain the organic phase (AOP) and the aqueous phase (APP). The more active AOP reported earlier, was further fractionated on a chromatography column packed with normal phase silica gel and eluted with a gradient (300ml each) mixture of n-hexane:chloroform:methanol (4:0:0, 3:1:0, 2:2:0, 1:3:0, 0:4:0, 0:3:1, 0:2:2, 0:1:3, 0:0:4) and the fractions pooled based on similarities from Thin layer chromatography fingerprint. Constituents in the active chromatography fraction(s) were characterized using Gas Chromatography- Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) technique. **Results:** Three pooled chromatography fractions A1, A2 and A3 were obtained in increasing order of polarity and A1 > A2 > A3 trend was observed for both urease inhibition and free radical scavenging activities. In the GC-MS analysis, three compounds (% abundance by area): (E)-2-[(Z)[(adamantan-1-yl) (phenyl)methylidene] amino)- 1,2-diaminoethene-1-thiol (18.9%), Oxime-, methoxy- phenyl (9.02%) and a polyacetylenic alcohol derivative: Eicosa-10-en-5-yn-1-ol (1.6 %) were conclusively characterised out of the thirteen detected compounds.

*Corresponding Author: Suleiman M.

Address: Department of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Email ✉: mikailu.suleiman@uniport.edu.ng

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Conclusion: Aside serving as biomarkers for phytochemical standardization, the presence of these compounds could offer a rationale for the anti-urease and free radical scavenging activities of *Microsorium pustulatum* leaves thus supporting some of its ethnobotanical uses, These compounds could also serve as leads for the development of drugs and ecofriendly urease inhibitors for improved crop production.

INTRODUCTION

Many of the plants within the family (Polypodiaceae) have been used traditionally for the treatment of wounds, ulcer, urinary tract disorder, viral, bacterial, fungal, antioxidant and in inflammatory states. As a follow-up to an earlier report on the anti-urease and free radical scavenging potentials of the leaves of the epiphytic fern *Microsorium pustulatum*,¹ this study is reporting the metabolites profile of an active chromatography fraction using Gas Chromatography- Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). Urease is a big enzyme that is within amidohydrolase family.² Commonly found in bacteria, fungi, algae, plants, some invertebrates and as soil enzyme. Urease catalyzes the hydrolysis of urea to form ammonia and carbon dioxide, hence automatically alters the pH of the surroundings to basicity level as a result of high concentration of ammonia produced. This resultant pH elevation is of diverse clinical and agronomic significance.³ Urease is a virulence factor for *Helicobacter pylori*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *S. saprophyticus* and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* among others that are associated with certain diseases in human and animals. It has been associated with the pathogenesis of kidney stones in acute pyelonephritis and other urinary tract infections. It is also implicated in arthritis, gastric intestinal infections and peptic ulcer.⁴ Its soil activity may damage crop yield as the urea on the surface of the soil transfers ammonia away from rhizosphere during the hydrolysis process because of its volatile nature. This has negative impact on the environment due to eventual acid rain or

nitrous oxide pollutant.⁵ On the other hand, in the management of oxidative stress, free radical scavenging compounds (antioxidants) helps to keep reactive oxygen (ROS) and reactive nitrogen (RNS) species in check, without being destabilized themselves. They help to promote longevity and good wellbeing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Reagents and solvents used in this study were of analytical grade and are products of JHD & Sigma Alderich Chemicals. Thiourea as reference standard and Urease test kits (Agape diagnostics Switzerland GmbH), 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and ascorbic acid as reference standard.

Sample collection and extraction

The leaves of *Microsorium pustulatum* was collected from the palm tree trunk in Rivers State University at Diobu in Obiakpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. The sample was identified by the Taxonomist with voucher specimen deposited within the herbarium in the Department of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy University of Port Harcourt. The plant material was air-dried for two weeks at room temperature and pulverized. A 200g quantity of the pulverized sample was defatted by cold macerated in n-hexane for 96 hours with intermittent agitation and fresh replacement of solvent after every 48 hours as earlier reported.¹ The defatted marc was then extracted similarly with acetone and the combined acetone filtrate concentrated using a rotary evaporator to afford the acetone extract as earlier reported by Olebunne *at al.*, and was used in this study.

Fractionation of the acetone extract

The most active acetone extract was partitioned into a water soluble (polar phase) and chloroform soluble (organic phase) fractions using separating funnel as reported earlier.¹ The organic phase (chloroform soluble fraction) coded "AOP" which was previously reported to be the more active was further fractionated using column chromatography. Briefly, approximately 1.3g of the AOP was pre-adsorbed on silica gel (Mesh 200-400) to form a homogeneous paste and allow to dry in a fume closet. The pre-adsorbed AOP was introduced into the normal phase column packed with the same silica gel (Mesh 200-400) as adsorbent to a height of 50cm and cotton wool was placed above it to protect it. The elution process was done using a gradient (300ml each) of n-hexane:chloroform: methanol (4:0:0, 3:1:0, 2:2:0, 1:3:0, 0:4:0, 0:3:1, 0:2:2, 0:1:3, 0:0:4). The eluates were collected at 50ml intervals and pooled based on observed R_f spots and color reaction with chromogenic spray reagent from TLC and three pooled fractions (A_1 , A_2 and A_3) were obtained and assessed for urease and free radical scavenging inhibitory activity.

Urease inhibitory analysis of the three extracts

The test was done using Phenol hypochlorite technique.⁶ Thiourea a known urease inhibitor was used as reference standard. The enzyme activity was measured through absorbance in the presence or absence of an inhibitor at 625nm using the spectrophotometer. The pooled chromatography fractions were assayed at 1 mg/ml. The reaction mixture (in the test tubes) containing BUN enzyme solution (1ml), sample solution (1ml) and urea (10 μ l) were mixed and then incubated for 10mins at 37⁰c, followed by the addition of 1 ml of a color developer. The mixture was further incubated for another 10 minutes, then 1ml of distilled water was added and the absorbance was taken. The percentage of urease inhibition was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of Urease} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test sample}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

The A_1 fractions was found to be more active and different concentrations of the A_1 fraction (0.1-1mg/ml) were examined and its median or half maximal inhibition concentration (IC_{50}) determined from regression analysis both for the urease and free radical scavenging inhibition activity.

Free radical scavenging assays

The DPPH radical scavenging assay was employed as modified.⁷ Briefly, a 1 ml aliquot of a 1mg/ml solution of the chromatography fractions A_1 , A_2 and A_3 were separately assayed for DPPH radical scavenging activity by adding 1ml of DPPH (0.05g/100ml of ethanol). The mixture was left in the dark for 30 min before reading at 517nm with ethanol as blank. The negative control contains ethanol in place of extract and ascorbic acid as reference standard. Radical scavenging activity was expressed as percentage and calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Scavenging} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of negative control} - \text{Absorbance of sample}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

The A_1 fractions was found to be more active and different concentrations of the A_1 fraction (0.05 - 1mg/ml) were examined and its median or half maximal inhibition concentration (IC_{50}) determined from regression analysis both for the urease and free radical scavenging inhibition activity.

GC-MS Analysis

The metabolite(s) present in the active pooled chromatography fraction A_1 were identified and characterized using GC-MS technique. 2 μ L of

sample dissolved in chloroform was injected into the column for the analysis. The Instrument: GC (Agilent model 7890B) coupled to a Mass Spectrometer (MS) detector (5977A MSD), was equipped with a DB-5MS capillary column (30m x 0.25 mm) and film thickness 0.25 µm). The oven temperature programming was set initially at 80°C and increased gradually to 200 °C at the rate of 15°C/minute. The temperature was further increased to 280°C at the rate of 5°C/ minute with a hold time of 5 minutes at 280 °C. The ion source set at 230°C. Helium was used as carrier gas at a

flow rate of 1ml/minute. Sample injection was done at a split ratio of 110:1. The MS ionization voltage was 70 eV with mass spectra data acquisition scanned from 50-550 m/z ratio. Metabolites assayed were identified from their retention time and their mass spectra fragmentation compared with that from the NIST library (2014) as well as critical review of the fragmentation scheme in line with the principles of mass spectrometry.^{8,9,10}

RESULTS

Figure 1. Urease inhibition activity of the three pooled chromatography fractions; A₁, A₂, A₃ from the AOP fraction of *Microsorium pustulatum* leaves at 1 mg/ml test concentration

Figure 2. Concentration dependent Urease inhibitory activity of most bioactive chromatographic fraction(A₁) from the organic phase of acetone extract of *Microsorium pustulatum* leaves.

Figure 3. Half maximum inhibition concentration (IC₅₀) of the referece standard and active chromatography fraction A1 from the leaves of *Microsorium pustulatum*

Figure 4. DPPH free radical inhibition activity of the three pooled chromatography fractions; A₁, A₂, A₃ from the AOP fraction of *Microsorium pustulatum* at 1 mg/ml test concentration

Figure 5. Concentration dependent DPPH free radical inhibition activity of the most active chromatography fraction A₁ from *Microsorium pustulatum*

Figure 6: Gas chromatogram of the most active chromatography fraction A₁ from *Microsorium pustulatum*

Table 1: Compounds characterized from GC-MS analysis of most active chromatography fraction A₁ from *Microsorium pustulatum*

S/N	Retention Time	Name of the compound	Chemical Structure	Chemical class	Molecular Formula	Mol. Ion peak (m/z unit)	Base peak (m/z unit)	Peak Area
1	2.922	Oxime-,methoxy-phenyl-		Alkaloid	C ₈ H ₉ NO ₂	151	133	9.9
2	11.081	Eicosa-10-en-5-yn-1-ol		Polyunsaturated fatty alcohol (polyacetylenic alcohol)	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ O	292	77	1.6
3	13.822	(E)-2-[(Z)[(adamantan-1-yl)(phenyl)methylidene]amino)-1,2-diaminoethene-1-thiol.		Alkaloid	C ₁₉ H ₂₅ N ₃ S	327	77	20.8

DISCUSSION

Fractionation of the AOP using normal phase column chromatography affords three pooled fractions A₁, A₂, A₃, based on their TLC

fingerprint. The pooled fraction A₁ eluted with 100% n-hexane, n-hexane: chloroform (3:1,2:2,1:3) was observed to be the most active with the percentage inhibition of 63.0% at the test concentration. It showed a concentration

dependent anti-urease activity with IC₅₀ of 0.12mg/ml (see Figure 3) though slightly less active compared to the reference standard (thiourea) with IC₅₀ of 0.08mg/ml. The GC-MS partial characterization of fraction A1 (see Figure 6 and Table 1) shows the presence of (E)-2-[(Z)-[(adamantan-1-yl)(phenyl)methylidene]amino]-1,2-diaminoethene-1-thiol. The terminal thiols part of the compound has the same structural resemblance with urea and thiolic compound (i.e. thiolate ions) react directly with the mettallocenter of urease.¹¹ Hence, may be accounted for its urease inhibitory activity and the adamantine derivatives are good antiviral and anticancer agents. There is also the presence of oxime-methoxy-phenyl. Triketone oxime has been reported as urease inhibitor.¹² Oxime has a good anti-inflammatory activity and are good chelators of metal i.e. easily form complexes with them. It can easily form complexes with nickel ion in urease enzyme, may be linked with the observed activity. A polyacetylenic alcohol Eicosa-10-en-5-yn-1-ol was also characterized. Polyacetylenic alcohols and related derivatives have been found to be of relevance in medicine and industry/cosmetology.¹³ Studies on the biological activity of polyacetylenes have indicated their potential to improve human health due to anticancer, antifungal, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and serotogenic effects. Falcarinol is a typical example isolated from carrot which aside used in protecting vegetable from fungal diseases, it showed biphasic and anticancer and anti-inflammatory activities. [14,15]

CONCLUSION

The partial characterization of adamantine and oxime derivatives from *Microsorium pustulatum* leaves with urease inhibitory activity in this study as earlier reported, further scientifically confirmed the use of this fern in ethno medicine for the

management of inflammatory conditions, wound healing(ulcer) and urinary tract infections.

Ethical approval: University of Port Harcourt Office of Research Management and Development, Research Ethic Committee (UPH/CEREMAD/REC/MM76/033) approved the work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Olebunne BO, Afierohe OE, Suleiman M, Abo KA. Evaluation of urease inhibitory and free radical scavenging activities of *Microsorium pustulatum* (G. Frost) copel leaves (Polypodiaceae). *International Journal of Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences Archive*. 2022, 4(1), 025-032
2. Holm L, Sander C. An evolutionary treasure: unification of a broad set of amidohydrolases related to urease. *Proteins*. 1997;28(1):72-82.
3. Mobley HLT, Hausinger RP. Microbial ureases: significance, regulation, and molecular characterization. *Microbiology Reviews*. 1989, 53, 85–108.
4. Hausinger RP, Mobley HL, Island MD. Molecular biology of microbial ureases. *Microbiological reviews*. 1995, 59(3), 451-480.
5. Artola E, Cruchaga S, Ariz I, Moran JF, Garnica M, Houdusse F. Effect of N-(n-butyl) thiophosphoric triamide on urea metabolism and the assimilation of ammonium by *Triticum aestivum* L. *Plant Growth Regulation*. 2011, 63, 73–79.
6. Weatherburn MW. (1967). Phenol hypochlorite reaction for determination of ammonia. *Analytical Chemistry*. 1967, 39, 971-974.

7. Afierohe OE, Ugbor ME. Evaluation of some antioxidant indices of the fresh flowers of *Harungana madagascariensis* Lam. Ex Poiret (Hypericaceae). *The Pharma Innovation Journal*. 2020, 9(4):142-146.
8. Adams RP. Identification of essential oils by ion mass spectroscopy. Academy Press, Inc New-York, 1989, 302pp.
9. Lei Z, Huhman DV, Sumner LW. Mass spectrometry strategies in metabolomics. *J Biol Chem*. 2011;286(29):25435-25442. doi:10.1074/jbc.R111.238691
10. Afierohe OE, Ugoeze KC. Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopic (GC-MS) Analysis of n-Hexane Extract of *Lentinus tuber-regium* (Fr) Fr (Polyporaceae) Syn *Pleurotus tuber regium* Fr sclerotia. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2014, 13 (11): 1911-1915.
11. Houimel M, Mach J, Corthesy-Theulaz L, Corthesy B, Fisch I. New inhibitors of *Helicobacter pylori* urease holoenzyme selected from phage- displayed peptide libraries, *European Journal of biochemistry*. 1999, 262, 774-780.
12. Tarun EI, Rubinov DB, Metelitz DI. (2004). Inhibition of urease by cyclic β -triketones and fluoride ions. *Applied Biochemistry and Microbiology* (Moscow). 2004, 40, 337- 344.
13. Noweck K, Grafahrend W. "Fatty Alcohols". *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*. Weinheim: Wiley-VCH. 2006.
14. Hansen SL, Purup S, and Christensen LP. Bioactivity of falcarinol and the influence of processing and storage on its content in carrots (*Daucus carota* L). *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture* 2003, 83, 1010-1017.
15. Metzger BT, Barnes DM, Reed JD. Purple Carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) Polyacetylenes Decrease Lipopolysaccharide-Induced Expression of Inflammatory Proteins in Macrophage and Endothelial Cells. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2008, 56, 10, 3554-3560

HOW TO CITE: Olebunne B. O., Afierohe O. E., Suleiman M.*, Abo K. A., Metabolites Profiling of An Anti-Urease and Free Radical Scavenging Fraction from the Acetone Leaves Extract of *Microsorium Pustulatum* (G. Frost) Copel (Polypodiaceae), *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 5, 117-125. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15321737>

